

REASONS FOR JOINING IN EQUIVALENCY EDUCATION IN KERALA

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Abstract

The study is about the equivalency programme of the Kerala State Literacy Mission Authority. The study intends to study the present status of equivalency programme of Kerala, to understand the reasons for joining Equivalency Programme, to identify the major motivational factors behind the Equivalency Learners, to find out the major challenges and hurdles of the Equivalency Programme and to put forth suggestions for improvement of the programme. Representative samples were collected from Kottayam, Ernakulam, Alapuzha and Kollam districts. 100 Samples of equivalency learners of Xth std. were selected for the study as samples. 15 equivalency teachers and 10 Centre Coordinators were selected and interviewed from each district for the study purpose. The study reveals that most of the learners belong to female category and most of the learners have poor economic and educational background. According to the study employment expectation, professional advancement, personal development and social status are the major motivational reasons for joining the continuing education programme in Kerala.

Introduction

It is the responsibility of the parents, society and /or state to see that all human beings in a modern society acquire or achieve a certain minimum level of education. This is generally called elementary education. Elementary education helps in effective participation in community life through instructions in basic facts and skills as of literacy, agriculture, dwelling, health and hygiene and citizenship and so on.

Education is given to individuals during their childhood starting with their formal schooling so as to make them fit for the society. In reality due to some reason or the other many individuals either get deprived of opportunity to have access to formal school or after access to it they may fail to acquire the desired level of elementary education. In such a case, it is more the state's responsibility to provide them with remedial opportunities / measures in their later years or adult life to promote in them this elementary education as remedial education. Such education is called fundamental education (UNESCO).

Continuing education (Venables 1976) programme includes those learning opportunities that are taken up after full-time schooling has ended or those learning opportunities that are taken up after the completion of initial education. Continuing education comes under the category of non-formal education.

Literates and neo-literate have to get facilities to maintain and develop their knowledge. Continuing education programme intends to provide an opportunity for further studies to literates, neo-literates and drop outs from schools etc. The core programme of continuing education is equivalency programme. At present IV, VII, X, XI, and XII equivalency examinations are conducted by the KSLMA under equivalency programme. Equivalency course at higher secondary level has been started by the government of Kerala. An equivalency board is functioning at the state level for the administration and supervision of equivalency programme. In short, continuing education programme provides an opportunity to the literates, neo literate, school drop outs and those people who are interested in continuous or lifelong education to continue their studies and to obtain certificate that are on a par with the certificate of formal system of education.

Title of the study:-

This research work has been entitled as 'Reasons for Joining in Equivalency Education in Kerala'.

Statement of the problem

The study is about the equivalency programme of the Kerala State Literacy Mission Authority which is getting greater recognition at present only because of its public acceptance. The researcher hopes that the study can throw some light on the various aspects of the equivalency programme like social significance, interests and needs of participants, major challenges, major motivational factors behind the equivalency learners and major hurdles of the equivalency programme, ways to improve the programme etc.

This study intends to understand the present status of the equivalency programme of the Kerala State Literacy Mission Authority. The study can also throw some light on the factors that are motivating equivalency learners for the successful completion of the course and to provide some feed back to the institution and its policy formulators for the planning, implementation, management and development of the equivalency courses.

Rationale of the Study

Education comes under service sector. As a service oriented institution, the Kerala State Literacy Mission Authority should know the interests and needs of its learners so that it can provide better service to them. The equivalency programme of the Kerala State Literacy Mission Authority has been attaining greater importance now a day's owing to its public acceptability. The educationists of the State Council for Education Research and Training should have enough knowledge as to the requirements of

the equivalency learners for the planning and preparation of effective curriculum for equivalency education. The state resource centre and the national literacy mission are interested in planning taking into consideration the needs and wants of the equivalency learners. The Government is also interested in the development of Equivalency Programme as it has greater public acceptance. Hence this study can throw some light in almost all spheres of equivalency programme like curriculum planning, policy formulation, planning and development of training programmes, better implementation monitoring and management of the programme, planning and development of innovative programmes and in the preparation of teaching materials etc.

Implication of the study

This study can throw some light on the factors that are motivating equivalency learners for the successful completion of the course and to provide some feed back to the institution and its policy formulators for the planning, implementation, management and development of the equivalency courses as more than 40,000 learners are joining in the equivalency programme per year and above 60% of the learners are from 10th standard. The study can help to make Kerala a state in which everyone has attained 10th standard.

Research Questions

The researcher sought answers to certain questions viz. what is the present status of equivalency programme in Kerala? What are the reasons for joining equivalency programme ?, What are the main motivational factors behind the equivalency learners ?, What are the problems faced by the learners? How they could tackle the problems? How they could find time to attend the classes? And who are the motivators? What are the suggestions for improvement of the programme?

Research questions have been prepared for equivalency learners and centre coordinators separately. Questionnaires were used to collect information from equivalency learners and interview schedule was used to collect information from centre coordinators.

Objectives of the study

The study intends the following objectives :

- (i) To study the present status of equivalency programme of Kerala.
- (ii) To understand the reasons for joining Equivalency Programme.
- (iii) To find out the major challenges and hurdles of the Equivalency Programme.
- (iv) To put forth suggestions for improvement of the programme.

Limitations of the study

Only 10th std. equivalency course have been given more importance in the present contest as more enrollments are seen than other levels of equivalency and only four districts (Kottayam, Ernakulam, Alappuzha, Kollam) have been covered for the study. Some respondents might not give very accurate information at the time of gathering information. There might be lack of co-operation from respondents. Respondents might be reluctant to reveal their attitude. Some respondents were busy. Therefore the reliability of the information is doubtful.

Universe of the Study

The study covers Southern districts of Kerala state. Representative samples were collected from Kottayam, Ernakulam, Alapuzha and Kollam districts. Questionnaires were issued to the equivalency learners of the above said districts and information were collected from Centre coordinators with the help of interview schedule. 10 Centre coordinators and 15 teachers were interviewed from each of the above mentioned districts.

Sample of the study

100 Samples of equivalency learners of Xth std. are selected under random sample method. 25 samples (equivalency learners) were selected from each of the above mentioned districts. This is applicable in the case of both the Questionnaire and Interview schedule. Equivalency learners of the Xth std. were selected for the study as samples. 15 equivalency teachers and 10 Centre coordinators were selected and interviewed from each district for the study purpose.

Tools and techniques used for data collection

Major tools used for the study are Questionnaire and Interview schedule. Questionnaire was used for equivalency learners to collect data and interview schedule was used to collect information from organizers/center coordinators of the equivalency programme.

Procedure of the data collection

Information has been collected using random sampling method. 25 equivalency learners from each district were given questionnaires visiting the district directly and explaining the questions before the equivalency classes of Xth std. students. 10 centre coordinators and 15 equivalency learners were called up to the district literacy mission offices of each district with the help of district coordinators and interviewed them directly using interview schedule. The investigator personally visited the Continuing Education Centres of all the four districts and met equivalency learners and Centre coordinators/teachers and data collected directly from them.

Procedure of data analysis

Simple statistical measures and methods have been used for analysis of the data. Interpretations have been done after scientific

analysis and suggestions have put forth on the basis of the analysis. Logical conclusions have been taken based on the analysis and interpretation.

It is concluded that the study can bring in to light a clear understanding as to the various aspects of the equivalency programme, reasons for its success, major challenges facing the programme and ways to improve the programme.

Review of Related Literature

So many books, research works and internet journals have been referred so as to get a clear picture on the subject. UNESCO manual for equivalency programme give more details. Data available at the State Literacy Mission and District Literacy Mission have been used.

Findings

1. The study reveals that 60% respondents come under female category and majority of them are in the age group of 15-35(58%)
2. As per study 30% of the respondents are Hindus, 34% are Christians and 36% are Muslims and also revealed that 18% of the respondents belongs to SC category, 16% belongs to ST category. 30% are in OBC category. 14% belongs to forward caste and 22% belongs to others category.
3. It is clear from the study that most of the respondents have passed IXth standard under formal education system and it is evident that 70% of the respondents are drop outs from the formal school and new comers to equivalency programme.
4. Eighty percent of the respondents are having annual income below Rs. 22000. Most of the family members of the respondents have poor educational background. Only 5% of the fathers, 6% of mothers, 30% brothers and 30% of the sisters have studied above Xth standard.
5. On an analysis, it is seen that 40% of the spouses have equivalency learner's background. 60% of the spouses are not equivalency learners.

6. The research finds that 80% of the children of the respondents have studied in Xth standard and above.
7. As per research, 10% of equivalency learners are govt. employees. 7% are private employees, 10% are wage labours, 3% are traditional labours and 70% come under others category

Table 1
Gender status of Respondents

It is found in the analysis of gender status of respondents that majority of equivalency learners are female (60%).

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	40	40%
Female	60	60%
Total	100	100%

This is because men have the responsibility to shoulder their family as they are income earners of the family.

Graph 1
Gender status of Respondents

Most of the respondents are female. This is because male literacy rate is higher than that of the females' and men are engaged in different occupation or employment in and around their district.

Table 2

Motivational Reasons for joining in the CE Programme

Financial matters	No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
	1	Employment expectation	31	31%
2	Professional Advancement	26	26%	
3	Income Advancement			
Non-financial matters	1	Higher study	33	33%
	2	Personal development	5	5%
	3	Skill development		
	4	Social status	5	5%
	5	Self esteem		
	6	Cognitive interest		
	7	Escapism		
	8	Stimulation		
	9	Facilitate change		
	10	Extrinsic interest		
	11	Social relationship		
	12	Social commitment		
	Total	100	100%	

Graph 2
Reasons for joining CE programme

Analysis regarding reasons for joining in the CE programme records that among 100 respondents, 31% of the respondents have under taken equivalency course with employment expectation, 26% for professional advancement, 33% for higher studies, 5% for personal development and another 5% for social status, 57% for financial matters and 43% for non-financial matters. The research reveals that equivalency learners are motivated mainly by financial reasons.

8. Most of the respondents have very good opinion about the CE programme. There was none with a moderate or not satisfactory opinion.
9. 57% of the respondents have under taken the equivalency course on account of financial reasons and 43% due to non-financial reasons.
10. Most of the respondents have been motivated by preraks. (45%) 30% are self-motivated, the rest are motivated by friends, (5%) relatives, (3%) and advertisement (7%) etc.
11. The study reveals that there is high degree of positive change in the confidence level, standard of living, quality of life, inherent potentialities, and knowledge level, Social status, friendly circle, discretionary powers and communication capabilities. 80% opined that there is no change in the income level.
12. There is remarkable degree of positive change in the attitude, mental health, and physical health of the respondents as a result of equivalency course. 100% of respondents felt a need of positive change in personal life. Education is a change agent.
13. Equivalency learners are getting excellent co-operation from the part of programme coordinators and teachers.
14. On an analysis, it is obvious that 70% respondents are interested in further studies under formal system.
15. 70% respondents are highly interested in further studies under non-formal education system.
16. It is very clear from the study that 80% prefer non-formal education system to formal education system.
17. All respondents are satisfied in the academic facilities and environment of the equivalency programme.
18. A great majority of equivalency learners (90%) think that they have to play remarkable role in the development of the society.
19. The research shows that 90% respondents agree that their level of adaptability towards circumstances has been increased as a result of equivalency education.
20. Most of the respondents (90%) have positive attitude towards future life after obtaining equivalency education.

21. It can be found from the study that 50% have left formal education due to family problems, 30% due to health problems, 10% due to financial problems and the rest 10% due to other problems.
22. 80% felt satisfaction during the time of equivalency course.
23. Most of the respondents (90%) felt that their level of creativity has been increased after the completion of equivalency course.
24. 60% felt difficulties in the completion of equivalency courses.
25. All respondents are satisfied in the training and development programmes provided for equivalency course.
26. Only 30% are satisfied in the career and development opportunities provided by the institution.
27. Most of the (90%) respondents are kept informed about the activities that go on in the KSLMA regarding their studies.
28. Only 20% felt positive change in their approach towards other people.
29. 60% of the equivalency programme organizers are motivated by superiors.
30. A major chunk of (90%) organizers are satisfied with the training and development programmes provided to them for equivalency course.
31. 60% organizers are satisfied in the career and development opportunities provided by the institution and the rest are not-satisfied.
32. All organizers are not satisfied with the honorarium provided by the institution.
33. It is true that 75% organizers are not satisfied with the financial support provided by the KSLMA.
34. It is very clear from the study that 90% organizers are not satisfied with the facilities provided to them as an organizer.
35. As per study 95% organizers opinioned that they are kept informed about the activities that go on in the KSLMA.
36. It is obvious that 96% organizers are satisfied in the supervision and guidance provided by the superiors.
37. It is a fact that 80% organizers are willing to take up more challenges in the equivalency programme.

38. It is clear that 86% organizers are satisfied in the co-operation provided to them by the equivalency teachers/instructors.

Major Suggestions

This study reveals that 60% of the respondents felt difficulties in the completion of equivalency course. Therefore, its cases should be identified by means of another study and necessary steps should be taken to alleviate these difficulties.

1. Better career and development opportunities should be provided to the equivalency learners.
2. Honorarium should be increased for preraks and teachers. Most of the organizers are not satisfied with the financial support provided by the KSLMA.
3. Necessary steps should be taken to provide adequate facilities to the equivalency organizers.
4. Study reveals that there is no major change in the income level of the learners. So income generating programmes should be considered.
5. Awareness about the equivalency program should be created among learners of formal education system. Equivalency system and formal education system should support each other.
6. The course fees of the different courses should be kept at the minimum level so as to accommodate everyone in the learning programs of the KSLMA.
7. The KSLMA should give importance to job oriented courses along with academic courses.
8. The KSLMA should take initiative to arrange awareness programs to its learners regarding their further opportunities and to facilitate opportunities for further studies.

Conclusion

It is concluded that the study can bring in to light a clear understanding as to the various aspects of the equivalency programme, reasons for its success, major challenges facing the programme and ways to improve the programme. Hence this study will be beneficial both to policy makers and equivalency learners as

the study take in to consideration almost all areas of equivalency programme including the requirements of equivalency learners and policy formulating authorities in order to make the study comprehensive and effective.

References :

1. **Ana Lusia De Oliveira Pires**(2007). The increasing role of higher education in life long learning process.
2. **Bhingarkar, D.B.** (1981). Implications of the concept of lifelong education for Social education.
3. **Caffarella, R. S.** (1993). Self-directed learning. In S.B. Merriam (Ed), An update on adult learning theory. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
4. **Cross, K.P.** (1981). Adult as learners: increasing the participation and facilitating learning. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
5. **Courtney, S** (1992). Voluntary participation in organized learning activities by adults.
6. **Dixit,** (1975). A study of educational need patterns of adults in the urban, rural and tribal communities of Rajasthan.
7. **Gadgil,** (1979). The need for continuing education programmes after completing the non formal education programme.
8. **Knowles, M.S.** (1970). The modern practice of adult education : Andragogy versus pedagogy. New York: Association press.
9. **Knox, A.B.** (1986). Helping Adults Learn. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
10. **Merriam, S.B. & Cafarella, R.S.** (1991). Learning in adulthood. San Francisco : Jossey-Bass.

11. **Mali, M.G.** (1974). Factors affecting retention of literacy among adult neo literates.
12. **Pillai, K. S.** (1978). Non formal education for agricultural workers and fisher men.
13. **Nair, T.S.** (2005). A Study on the Performance of Continuing Education Program in Kerala.
14. **Nair, T.S.** (2013). A Study on the VigyanJyothy Project (Total Primary Education Programme) of Kasargode District.
15. **UNESCO** Manual for equivalency programme.

